

Synthesis and Antifungal Activity of some Substituted 1,3,4-Oxadiazolo[3,2-*a*]-*s*-triazin-5-phenyl-7-thione and Imidazo[2,1-*b*]-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5-one

C. S. ANDOTRA* and POONAM SHARMA

Department of Chemistry, University of Jammu, Jammu-180 004

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In continuation of our interest in the five- and six-membered heterocycles containing nitrogen and oxygen atoms, such as 1,3,4-oxadiazoles, *s*-triazine and imidazole derivatives having various biological activities^{1,2}, it was considered worthwhile to synthesise bridgehead nitrogen heterocycles containing the above mentioned rings like 1,3,4-oxadiazolo[3,2-*a*]-*s*-triazin-5-phenyl-7-thione and imidazo[2,1-*b*]-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5-one.

- 2.3a:** Q = 2,4-dimethoxy-5-ethylphenyl
a': Q = 2,4-diethoxy-5-ethylphenyl
b: Q = 2,4-dimethoxy-5-n-propylphenyl
b': Q = 2,4-diethoxy-5-n-propylphenyl
c: Q = 2,4-dimethoxy-5-n-butylphenyl
c': Q = 2,4-diethoxy-5-n-butylphenyl
d: Q = 2-methoxy-4-ethoxy-5-ethylphenyl
e: Q = 2-ethoxy-4-methoxy-5-ethylphenyl

The compounds (Table 1) were screened for antifungal activity against *H. oxyzae*, *A. flavous*, *Penicillium* and *F. oxysporium* by adopting inhibition zone technique⁴.

TABLE 1—SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2 AND 3

Compd. no.	m.p. °C	$\nu_{\max}$ cm ⁻¹	δ
2a	172°	2 900, 1 670, 1 575, 1 465, 1 210, 1 170, 910, 850	1.14 (3H, t, <i>J</i> 6.5 Hz, CH ₂ CH ₃), 2.5 (2H, q, <i>J</i> 6.5 Hz, benzylic), 4.1 (6H, s, 2 × OCH ₃), 7.4 (7H, m, ArH)
2a'	165°	3 000, 1 610, 1 520, 1 466, 1 275, 1 185, 1 040, 912	1.12 (3H, t, <i>J</i> 6.5 Hz, CH ₂ CH ₃), 1.55 (6H, t, <i>J</i> 6.0 Hz, 2 × OCH ₂ CH ₃), 2.56 (2H, q, <i>J</i> 6.5 Hz benzylic), 4.21 (4H, q, <i>J</i> 6.0 Hz, 2 × OCH ₂ CH ₃), 7.6 (m, <i>J</i> 6.5, ArH)
2b	169°	2 990, 1 620, 1 545, 1 460, 1 280, 1 170, 1 045, 990, 810	0.96 (3H, t, <i>J</i> 6.5 Hz, CH ₂ CH ₃), 1.2 (2H, m, <i>J</i> 6.5 Hz, CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃), 2.35 (2H, t, <i>J</i> 6.5 Hz, benzylic), 3.59 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 3.66 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 7.41 (7H, m, <i>J</i> 6.5 Hz ArH)
2b'	162°	2 920, 1 624, 1 550, 1 470, 1 285, 1 190, 1 050, 1 010, 970, 830	0.96 (3H, t, <i>J</i> 6.5 Hz, CH ₂ CH ₃), 1.50 (6H, m, <i>J</i> 6.0 Hz, 2 × OCH ₂ CH ₃), 2H, m, <i>J</i> 6.5 Hz, CH ₂ CH ₃), 2.52 (2H, t, <i>J</i> 6.5 Hz, benzylic), 4.15 (4H, q, <i>J</i> 6 Hz, 2 × OCH ₂ CH ₃), 7.7 (7H, m, <i>J</i> 6.5 Hz ArH)
2c	170–71°	2 900, 1 626, 1 530, 1 490, 1 270, 1 185, 1 110, 1 070, 1 020, 980, 800	0.51 (3H, t, <i>J</i> 6.5 Hz, CH ₂ CH ₃), 1.25 (4H, m, <i>J</i> 6.5 Hz, CH ₂ CH ₂), 2.28 (2H, t, <i>J</i> 6.5 Hz, benzylic), 3.66 (6H, s, 2 × OCH ₃), 7.3 (7H, m, ArH)
2c'	175–77°	2 980, 1 650, 1 260, 1 570, 1 060, 1 011, 945, 750	0.54 (3H, t, <i>J</i> 6.5 Hz, CH ₂ CH ₃), 1.24 (4H, m, <i>J</i> 6.5 Hz, CH ₂ CH ₂), 2.30 (2H, t, <i>J</i> 6.5 Hz, benzylic), 4.15 (4H, q, <i>J</i> 6.0 Hz, 2 × OCH ₂ CH ₃), 7.8 (7H, m, <i>J</i> 6.5 Hz, ArH)
2d	178–79°	2 980, 1 625, 1 560, 1 510, 1 450, 1 290, 1 177, 1 110, 1 080, 960, 775	1.17 (3H, t, <i>J</i> 6.5 Hz – CH ₂ CH ₃), 1.57 (3H, t, <i>J</i> 6.0 Hz, OCH ₂ CH ₃), 2.40 (2H, q, <i>J</i> 6.5 Hz, benzylic), 3.63 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 4.20 (2H, q, <i>J</i> 6.0 Hz, OCH ₂ CH ₃), 7.3 (7H, m, <i>J</i> 6.5 Hz, ArH)

Table-1(contd.) **Experimental**

2e	180-81°	2 995, 1 627, 1 560, 1 540, 1 465, 1 260, 1 170, 1 120, 1 072, 980, 830	1 18 (3H, t, J 6.5 Hz, CH ₂ CH ₃), 1 44 (3H, t, J 6.0 Hz, OCH ₂ CH ₃), 2 40 (2H, q, J 6.5 Hz, benzylic), 3 69 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 4 05 (2H, q, J 6.0 Hz, OCH ₂ CH ₃)	—
3a	168°	2 975, 1 725, 1 640, 1 275, 1 065, 945, 670	—	—
3a'	175-76°	2 900, 1 736, 1 645, 1 275, 1 490, 1 050, 970, 725	—	—
3b	171°	2 934, 1 726, 1 634, 1 260, 1 485, 1 045, 970, 732	—	—
3b'	183°	2 960, 1 740, 1 650, 1 260, 1 534, 1 070, 970, 720, 645	—	—
3c	173°	2 970, 1 726, 1 670, 1 275, 1 545, 1 075, 970, 645	—	—
3c'	187-89°	2 990, 1 736, 1 660, 1 270, 1 540, 1 075, 944, 670	—	—
3d	190-92°	2 985, 1 740, 1 643, 1 272, 1 545, 1 075, 950, 670	—	—
3e	183°	2 979, 1 738, 1 640, 1 269, 1 542, 1 073, 948, 667	—	—

The results reveal that compound **2b'** is most active against *H. oxysae* (zone of inhibition 22 mm) in oxadiazolotriazine series. Compounds **2b'**, **2c** and **2e** are active (7-17 mm) against other three fungi. Compounds **2b** and **2c'** are not active against any of the four fungi. In imidazo-oxadiazole series, compounds **3a'**, **3b'** and **3c'** are active (7-18 mm) against all the four fungi. Compounds **3c** is active (7-10 mm) against *Penicillium* and *H. oxysae* and **3e** is active (8-9 mm) against *A. flavous* and *H. oxysae*. Compounds **3b** and **3d** are not active against any of the four fungi.

M.ps. were taken in open capillary tube and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP 2000 spectrophotometer and nmr spectra (CDCl₃) using TMS as internal standard. Elemental analysis was performed on a Heraeus CHN analyser.

2,4-Dialkoxy-5-alkylbenzaldehydes were converted into the corresponding semicarbazones which were cyclised³ by bromine in glacial acetic acid in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate to give 2-amino-5-aryl-substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazoles.

N-[5-(2,4-Dialkoxy-5-alkylphenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl]-*N*-benzoylthiourea (**1**): 2-Amino-5-(2,4-dialkoxy-5-alkylphenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole (0.01 mol) was refluxed with benzoyl isothiocyanate (0.01 mol) in acetone for 2 h. The resulting fine crystals were recrystallised from ethanol.

2-(2,4-Dialkoxy-5-alkylphenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazolo[3,2-a]s-triazin-5-phenyl-7-thione (**2**): A mixture **1** (0.01 mol), PCl₅ (0.11 mol) and POCl₃ (15 ml) was refluxed for 2 h and then crushed ice added to it. The solid thus obtained was crystallised from methanol.

2-(2,4-Dialkoxy-5-alkylphenyl)imidazo[2,1-b]-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5-one (**3**): 2-Amino-5-(2,4-dialkoxy-5-alkylphenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole (0.01 mol) was refluxed with chloroacetic acid (0.02 mol) and anhydrous sodium acetate in dry methanol for 8-10 h. The product was cooled, filtered, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol.

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